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Technical paper: Interoperability is essential for ensuring digital sustainability

*Part of D4.4: Socio-environmental Assessment of Last-mile and
Edge Technological Solutions*

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1. Introduction- The impact of data on agriculture

The agricultural sector has witnessed a digital transformation driven by technologies and data-driven solutions, similar to the transformations occurring in many other sectors. These advanced digital services, mainly designed for agronomic practices, are also known as smart farming or digital agriculture. These services benefit from cutting-edge technologies and methods including Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Precision Agriculture (PA). The fragmented use of these technologies results in silos in which data often remains unfindable, inaccessible, incompatible, and not (re)usable. To maximize the potential of digital agriculture, addressing these silos and enhancing data interoperability is essential.

2. Why – Reflecting on urgent questions in the domain of interoperability

There are many forthcoming sustainability challenges that require approaches with different levels of scope and magnitude, such as urban and rural areas as well as company (farm)- level, regional and, or, (trans)national. To analyse and assess the environmental, social, and economic impact of digital services, data integration becomes an essential step in this process. However, the aforementioned complexity also indicates an increased heterogeneity of data to perform, for example, environmental and/or social Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) within the agricultural and rural areas. The integration of heterogeneous data for digital services requires interoperability between many levels, such as legal, organisational, technical and semantical. Interoperability is a critical necessity to ensure that users can benefit from different brands of machinery and digital services smoothly, so that, they can choose from a wide range of alternatives according to their needs and budget. In this regard, interoperability is also critical for undistorted competition and fostered innovation. The European Interoperable Europe Academy was attended to learn more on existing best-practices, standards, and harmonization tools to ensure interoperability where needed for the application of holistic sustainability assessments.

[The Interoperable Europe Academy 2024](#), a jointly organised two-days event by KU Leuven and [the Directorate General for Digital Services \(DIGIT\)](#), focused on public sector interoperability and improving understanding on the Interoperable Europe Act (IEA) and how to set up interoperable digital public services with guiding materials such as [the European Interoperability Framework \(EIF\)](#). With 200 physical and 400 online participants from governmental organizations, companies, and academia, the event offered workshops and deepen knowledge among public servants, policymakers, and scientists. [The Pioneer MSc program](#), funded by the EU, is offered to bridge the gap between public services and information systems, including many opportunities for scholarships and internships. DIGIT and [the Service public fédéral \(SPF BOSA\)](#) shared their insights, emphasizing their extensive experience of over 20 years in discussing interoperability.

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A definition for interoperability that was provided during the academy is:

“Interoperability is a key factor in making a digital transformation possible. It allows administrative entities to electronically exchange meaningful information in ways that are understood by all parties. It addresses all layers that impact the delivery of digital public services in the EU, including legal, organisational, semantic and technical aspects.”

With this definition as a baseline, in this blog we aim to reflect on urgent questions in the domain of interoperability, including: To what extent are existing best-practices, standards, and harmonization tools applicable for the agricultural, rural and coastal areas to perform holistic sustainability assessments? Or, how do we define public services in terms of digital services that are developed in projects financed by both governments, business, and other value-chain actors? Notably, this blog contains many web links to other sources to enrich the information in such a way that it provides a comprehensive understanding of the interoperability discussions within the European Union.

3. Results- Learnings from the Academy

After the [general introduction](#), a series of messages were presented across different plenary and parallel sessions. For instance, the [first plenary session](#) deep-dived into [the Interoperable Europe Act \(IEA\)](#) and addressed the question: What do interoperability and IEA mean for digital government across the EU? Some main messages from this session include the fact that interoperability and the IEA are crucial for digital government across the EU. The IEA has been developed since 2010 and encompasses various aspects, such as interoperability assessment ([Article 3](#)), sharing and reusing interoperability solutions ([Article 4](#)), and frameworks that cover legal, organisational, and semantic dimensions ([Article 6](#)). The IEA recommends interoperable solutions via the Interoperable Europe Solutions ([Article 7](#)) and provides a user-friendly Interoperable Europe Portal for sharing findings and reports ([Article 8](#)). Moreover, another highlighted message was about regulations like [the Digital Single Gateway Regulation \(DSGR\)](#) that facilitate cross-border users' access (equally) to services, information and procedures. It was noted that there is a shift from ‘documents’ to ‘data’, in which Estonia was mentioned as an advanced example in this domain. Also, divisions like [DG GROW](#) and [DG REFORM](#) aim to assist public administrations in digital strategies, transformation, and data sharing in the single market, industry, entrepreneurship and small businesses. Importantly, the Interoperable Europe Act does not force existing systems to change but fosters better interoperability and data exchange.

Another plenary session addressed the topic of “Decoding the Interoperable Europe Act – turning the Act into action”. This session focused on discussing the challenges of *community engagement* in interoperability efforts. Emphasis was placed on reaching out and involving national and, especially, *local-level communities*. Participants noted the availability of various online courses on Interoperable Europe but questioned the coherence of the learning path. One analogy that was mentioned is:

“The sauce keeps the lasagna together. Interoperability is the sauce and makes the lasagna tastier and healthier”

After the plenary sessions, several parallel workshops were organised. [One contribution](#) provided from a research perspective, was the needs to inform about the future discussions on the evolution of the European Interoperability Framework (EIF). The EIF, first published in 2010 and updated in 2017, is commonly agreed approach to deliver interoperable public services within the European Union, by defining basic interoperability guidelines in the form common principles, models, and recommendations. This research perspective session, organized by [Joint Research Centre \(JRC\)](#), [TU Twente](#), and KU Leuven, informed the participants on discussions for the development of the EIF. The discussion traced back to 1995, with notable milestones in 2001 and 2017 when the EIF was updated. The EIF comprises 12 principles, including inclusion, and encompasses various layers such as legal, organisational, technical, and semantic (Figure 1). While the governance layer deals with the

different EIF implementations, the organisation layer is about the harmonisation of business process models. Different EIF domain implementations were highlighted. Sub-groups of the EIF domain discussed diverse topics including:

- *Interoperability recommendations*
- *Aligning frameworks & data interoperability*
- *Introducing a new EIF layer focusing on cultural interoperability to address skills and capacity needs as cultural differences impact interoperability Expectations & moving to actions.*

Figure 1: Adapted layers of the European Interoperability Framework (EIF). The Interoperability Governance forms the framework around the layers.

The main key take-aways from the sub-group “Aligning frameworks & data interoperability”, include a discussion that highlighted common principles and diverse definitions as challenges in achieving alignment of interoperability frameworks, using [INSPIRE](#) as an example. In the agri-food domain, fragmentation present significant challenges, along with the need to navigate between various standards applicable to the domain and its sub-domains. Reference data from the EU Publication Office illustrates also this complexity, with over 100 lists of the countries in the EU. Open data catalogues and technical standards like [the Data Catalogue Vocabulary \(DCAT\)](#) are crucial, alongside consideration of national and sectoral frameworks and best practices. A notable quote is:

“Data without interoperability is useless”.

Furthermore, various frameworks on data quality were discussed, emphasizing its foundational role for alignment. An approach in agri-food emphasizes use-case-driven determinations to scope the context and degree of interoperability. For example, the [Minimum Interoperability Mechanisms \(MIMs\)](#) and obstacles to their application in the EIF were discussed. Discussion on hopes for the future was rather pessimistic, mentioning the [Catch-22](#) situation as an example to obstacles to cross-border services. Suggestions included the establishment of a guiding board and recognition of cultural ethics. Lastly, the call of expression for experts is mentioned, as well EIF courses, the National Interoperability Framework (NIF), and the importance of digital skills were also highlighted.

In a follow-up panel discussion, the “Academic view of the Interoperable Europe Act” was discussed with a moderator and five representatives from the academia. This discussion emphasized the significance of IEA for the EU but highlighted several challenges, including the need for an ‘overarching’ understanding. A remarkable quote is:

“Interoperability is standardisation”

A provocative message was to focus directly towards achieving real interoperability rather than merely discussing the act and mechanisms. Experiences highlighted the existence of distinct worlds within interoperability efforts, characterized by differing languages, communication methods, processes, and politics. Clarity regarding *which* services require interoperability is crucial, while it should be noted that the scope is often likely broader than initially perceived.

The [discussion](#) on “Develop skills with the Interoperable Europe Academy” was between eight participants and one moderator. Key highlights include the offering of the Interoperable Europe Academy of skill-learning opportunities. Different countries as represented in the panel mentioned for example, in Portugal, interoperability is one of 12 selected skills, while Romania faces challenges with its development in this area. Poland demonstrates significant progress and ambitious plans, exemplified by governmental architecture training. While Spain, on the other hand, has a national regulation concerning interoperability degrees. The value model for interoperability, particularly in monetary terms, was questioned by the participants. From a research perspective, interoperability involves both soft skills (legal, organizational) and hard skills (technical). Two last suggestions include a “train the trainers” approach and optimizing existing applications rather than creating new ones, illustrated by the example of ‘passport’ applications.

The second day started with a panel [discussion](#) on cross-border sharing and reuse (article 4) in practice between five participants and one moderator. The morning panel discussions showed multiple use cases from practise where interoperability was achieved. Ranging from the verification of credentials to the traffic and urban sector. Some examples include the [eIDAS which stands for Electronic identification, authentication, and trust services](#). With eIDAS, European member states have agreed to use the same concepts, levels of reliability, and mutual digital infrastructure. A part of the regulation involves the cross-border use of European-recognized login credentials. Another example is the [European Digital Infrastructure Consortium \(EDIC\)](#) which is a tool made available to member states as part of the policy program for the [Digital Decade 2030](#) to accelerate and simplify the setup and execution of multi-country projects. EDIC will facilitate the achievement of the overall goals and objectives of the Digital Decade. One last interesting example was the mobility data space which used [Solid](#) Pods as technology to achieve interoperability and sovereignty.

The parallel [workshop](#) on AI and Semantic Interoperability revealed some new interesting technical insights. The presented work derives from [Semantic Interoperability Centre Europe \(SEMIC\)](#), which is an initiative by the European Commission aimed at promoting and supporting semantic interoperability for public administrations across Europe. It provides guidelines, tools, and best practices to ensure that data can be exchanged and understood across different systems and EU member states. In the presentation a data modelling chatbot was presented, based on Microsoft Azure. The [Metadata for Learning and Development Cooperation Application Profile \(MLDCAT-AP\)](#) was presented and is a standardized metadata schema designed to improve interoperability and data sharing in the education and learning domains. It provides a common framework for describing learning resources, facilitating better discovery, reuse, and integration across educational platforms and systems. This is currently ongoing work in the form of an [open consultation](#) in the Dutch context, coordinated by Geonovum. The platforms, tools, and libraries that were used are among others: [Hugging Face](#), [Kaggle](#), [PyTorch](#), [Azure ML](#), and [ReSpec HTML](#).

4. Conclusion - Interoperability is essential for digital sustainability

In summary, the development and adoption of (data) standards to achieve interoperability are pivotal for creating a connected and collaborative ecosystem for digitalisation in rural, forestry, aquatic, and agricultural areas. As the agricultural industry continues to embrace technology, the establishment of these foundational elements will play a crucial role in unlocking the full potential of digital solutions, ultimately contributing to global food security, resource conservation, and the overall sustainability of agriculture. With standardisation and smooth interoperability, users can use various devices and services together and they can switch between companies when necessary. This would serve a continuous development of the sector with innovative start-ups and vivid competition among companies, which develop digital services or devices. More presentations (from other parallel workshops) can be found on [the event page](#). These resources provide further insights and examples of successful interoperability initiatives.

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